

DETECTION OF PERMEABILITY VARIATIONS FOR EARLY QUALITY ASSESSMENT IN LIQUID COMPOSITE MOLDING

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1 Introduction

Composite structures' quality and performances are negatively affected by problems during the manufacturing, e.g. fiber misalignment or void content higher than an allowed value [1]. Production of parts with a reproducible quality is particularly challenging in Liquid Composite Molding (LCM) technologies, like Resin Transfer Molding (RTM), Vacuum Assisted Resin Infusion (VARI) and their variants, since the manufacture by LCM is very sensitive to process and material variations [2].

LCM technologies are based on the impregnation of a fibrous fabric preform by a reactive resin system: in these processes, quality issues depend mostly on the resin flow within the preform. The essential parameter for the description of the impregnation is the fabric permeability, a measure of the effective free space available for fluid flow in the porous preform. Knowledge of the actual permeability distribution provides a substantial contribution to the part quality assessment because: (I) fiber misalignments/textile variations have a local impact on the permeability, which affects the flow-front pattern; (II) flow velocity and flow-front pattern have an influence on the final void content within the part [3, 4].

In literature, it is shown that permeability can vary within a certain range, even under well-controlled conditions [5-7]. In recent years, many works have outlined methods to characterize textile permeability; nevertheless, a standard experimental procedure is still missing and the measurements are typically prone to errors [5, 7-11]. Additionally, the majority of the contributions issued do not account for the effective spatial changes of permeability values, resulting from the above-mentioned process variations during real preform impregnations.

The present work proposes an approach to address the problem to identify local changes of permeability along the flow direction during an LCM process. In previous studies [2, 12], an experimental/numerical methodology for flow monitoring has been introduced. The methodology made use of a discrete number of pressure transducers, embedded in the mold, to acquire information for estimating the flow-front positions along defined flow paths. At the time step of interest, single pressure values, from only a small number of sensors, allowed for determining the current flow-front, even in complex cavity geometry. To provide accurate flow-front estimations, the methodology required the knowledge of the local permeability distribution, which is not usually the case in real environments.

The present study proposes an extension of the aforementioned methodology: the pressure history at the sensor locations is considered, in order to obtain information on unknown permeability changes. The methodology hereby presented focuses on rectilinear one-dimensional injections. Nevertheless, the main idea can be similarly applied to radial injections, with varying permeability along the impregnation radius, and possibly extended to more complex two-dimensional cases, treating them as multiple one-dimensional flows [13] with varying cross sections along the flow paths [2].

In the next section, after introduction of the used model for fluid flow in fibrous reinforcement, the method for permeability mapping is presented. Subsequently, in section 3, the potential of the methodology is investigated by applying it to various one-dimensional virtual injection cases, where varying permeability distributions are inputted. Results including comparison of actual and reconstructed permeability distributions and flow-front positions are shown and discussed. In the last

section, conclusions are summarized and an outlook is outlined.

2 Methodology for permeability mapping

2.1 Flow modeling in impregnation processes

The resin flow in porous fibrous reinforcements is typically modeled through Darcy's law:

$$\mathbf{v} = -\frac{\mathbf{K}}{\eta} \nabla p \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{K} is the permeability tensor, η the resin viscosity, p the fluid pressure and \mathbf{v} the volume averaged velocity (also called Darcy velocity). The latter differs from the flow-front velocity v_f (or inherent resin velocity) by a factor φ , which represents the porosity (actual volume fraction of free space available for resin flow):

$$\mathbf{v}_f = \mathbf{v} / \varphi \quad (2)$$

Darcy's law (1) is combined with the continuity equation, which, for incompressible fluids like resins, states:

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} = 0 \quad (3)$$

leading to:

$$\nabla \cdot \left(\frac{\mathbf{K}}{\eta} \nabla p \right) = 0 \quad (4)$$

Equation (4) represents the basis for the methodology introduced in the following subsections. It expresses the fundamental relationship from which to derive the pressure distribution in the mold cavity regions filled with resin (saturated regions) at a certain impregnation time.

Yet equation (4) is not sufficient to describe the fluid flow through the whole cavity and it is traditionally further coupled with (1) to account for the resin movement when simulating an impregnation process. In this work, virtual injection experiments are used as benchmark to apply the permeability mapping methodology. They have been simulated using the model of Klunker et al. [14], which is based on the combination of (1) and the continuity equation in both saturated and unsaturated regions:

$$\varphi \frac{\partial S}{\partial t} - \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{\mathbf{K}}{\eta} \nabla p \right) = 0 \quad (5)$$

where S is a saturation term, with values ranging from 0 (in the cavity region not filled with the resin yet) to 1 (in the cavity region already filled with the resin), which has the following expression:

$$S = \frac{2}{\pi} \arctan(\alpha p) \quad (6)$$

with the numerical shape factor α determining the length of the transition at the flow-front between the unfilled region and the fully saturated one (in this paper, $\alpha = 0.01 \text{ Pa}^{-1}$). It is noticeable that (5) reduces to (4) in the cavity region completely filled with resin (where S tends to the constant value of 1).

2.2 Rectilinear flow with varying permeability

In one-dimensional injection case, assuming a constant viscosity along the length, equation (4) becomes:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(K(x) \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} (x) \right) = 0 \quad (7)$$

In other words, at each impregnation time, the product of the local permeability value and the local pressure gradient is spatially constant. As an example, Figure 1 illustrates, at a fixed time, the pressure profile in a laminate characterized by two distinct zones, in which the permeability shows two different constant values. In the example of Figure 1, a pressure sensor located in x_s measures the resin pressure p_s at the considered time. The pressure p_{in} at the injection point x_{in} is either set known or measured with another sensor external to the mold cavity. Naming K_s the permeability value between x_{in} and x_s , from (7) it derives:

$$K(x) \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} (x) = K_s \frac{p_s - p_{in}}{x_s - x_{in}} \quad (8)$$

The 1D flow-front velocity can be obtained by the combination of (1) and (2) applied at the flow-front position x_f :

$$v_f = -\frac{K(x_f) \partial p}{\eta \varphi \partial x} (x_f) \quad (9)$$

Using (8) in (9), v_f can be written as function of the pressure drop from the inlet and the sensor location:

$$v_f = -\frac{K_s}{\eta\varphi} \frac{p_s - p_{in}}{x_s - x_{in}} \quad (10)$$

Equation (10) allows for determining the flow-front velocity at each injection time, regardless of the actual permeability variations along the flow direction. The flow-front position x_f over the process time t can be easily derived by an integration of v_f :

$$x_f(t) = x_s + \int_{t_s}^t v_f(\tau) d\tau \quad (11)$$

where t_s is the time at which the resin reaches the sensor position (of course, no information on the flow is available before that point). Equation (10) - and consequently (11) - requires an input for K_s , which can be either known a priori (equal to a reference or undisturbed permeability value of the preform) or calculated from t_s and $x_f(t_s) = x_s$, using the analytical 1D solution for the flow-front (e.g. in [3]). In this latter case, the fact that the permeability may be varying between x_{in} and x_s has no relevance, since the resulting permeability K_s is calculated as an equivalent constant.

Equations (10) and (11) require as input also the value of the porosity φ , which may show deviations from the designed value, as the permeability K varies along the laminate length. Anyway, permeability and porosity variations are linked together; equations like the formula of Kozeny-Carman [15] are typically used to express their relationship. Additionally, it has to be stated that changes of φ have usually a lower influence on the flow in comparison with permeability deviations, as it can be derived from (2) and the above-cited Kozeny-Carman equation (for instance, a permeability variation of 20% corresponds approximately to a porosity variation of only 4%). Thus, in this work the porosity is assumed to be constant.

2.3 Permeability profile reconstruction

An iterative algorithm has been devised to automatically estimate the permeability profile. It is based on the fact that, at each fixed impregnation time, the resin flux (and, consequently, the resin velocity) is constant over the laminate length through zones with different permeability values, as it is deducible from (7) and (10).

To map the permeability profile, the impregnation time is discretized in a number of time steps, at which the actual flow-front position is calculated using (11). The permeability values are considered constant between two subsequent flow-front positions. In any case, the spacing can be taken as fine as required by choosing a time period small enough.

At a certain time step t_i , the working principle of the iterative algorithm is illustrated with reference to Figure 2, showing (similarly to Figure 1) the pressure distribution along the laminate, where x_f and x_v represent the flow-front position at the current time step t_i and at the previous time step t_{i-1} .

The objective of the algorithm for the current time step t_i is to determine the permeability value K_v in the zone between x_v and x_f . As starting condition, the permeability distribution between x_s and x_v is known (it results from the preceding time steps); and, hence, an equivalent permeability K_{eq} can be calculated, in order to simplify the effective pressure drop to a linear decrease from x_s to x_v (as in Figure 2). The equivalent permeability has the following expression:

$$K_{eq} = \frac{x_v - x_s}{\int_{x_s}^{x_v} \frac{dx}{K(x)}} \quad (12)$$

The detection of K_v is done in two steps. First, the pressure value p_v at x_v is calculated from (8), using the concept of equivalent permeability in (12):

$$\begin{aligned} K_s \frac{p_s - p_{in}}{x_s - x_{in}} &= K_{eq} \frac{p_v - p_s}{x_v - x_s} \\ \Leftrightarrow p_v &= p_s + (p_s - p_{in}) \frac{K_s}{K_{eq}} \frac{x_v - x_s}{x_s - x_{in}} \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Second, the unknown permeability value is found, applying again (8), as it follows:

$$\begin{aligned} K_s \frac{p_s - p_{in}}{x_s - x_{in}} &= K_v \frac{p_f - p_v}{x_f - x_v} \\ \Leftrightarrow K_v &= K_s \frac{x_f - x_v}{x_s - x_{in}} \frac{p_s - p_{in}}{p_f - p_v} \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

where p_f is the pressure at the flow-front position, which is assumed to be equal to the pressure at the outlet [2].

Once K_v is found, the procedure is repeated for the subsequent time steps until the flow-front reaches the outlet x_{fin} . In the end, by using data from a single pressure sensor embedded in the mold, the algorithm tracks the complete actual permeability profile along the laminate length and flow-front advancement with time for rectilinear injection cases.

3 Results and discussion

The effectiveness of the methodology above illustrated has been investigated through several virtual injection tests. One-dimensional flow simulations have been performed using a Finite Element Method to solve (5), where arbitrary permeability functions have been introduced. Boundary conditions and other parameters used in all the experiments are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Parameters for virtual injection test

Parameter	Symbol	Value
Injection pressure	p_{in}	1 bar
Vent pressure	p_f	0 bar
Laminate length	$l = x_{fin} - x_{in}$	1 m
Resin viscosity	η	0.1 Pa·s
Porosity	ϕ	0.5

From the virtual injection tests, pressure data at defined sensor positions have been inputted into the algorithm, which performed the permeability profile reconstruction according to the aforementioned methodology. In the following, relevant results, regarding comparison of input/reconstructed permeability distributions and flow-front tracking, are shown and discussed.

Figure 3 shows the outcome of the methodology's application in a simple case, where the permeability stays constant along the laminate length. It is noticeable that such constant value is adequately estimated. The highest discrepancies from the given permeability appear in proximity of the sensor position; a peak is observed at the algorithm's starting point (deviation around 20%), followed by waning oscillations, which are ascribable to numerical errors in the injection simulation. To avoid such miscalculations, the output permeability is smoothed and the resulting deviations lay within the 1% of the nominal input value.

Figure 4 illustrates the results for an injection test, in which a relatively high (one order of magnitude) jump of permeability is encountered. It can correspond, for instance, to the case of variation of the thickness or the number of layers or the kind of fabric in the stacking sequence of the laminate. Also in this situation, the proposed approach is able to recognize the permeability profile, detecting successfully the deviation from the nominal value. Figure 5 demonstrates that also the flow-front advancement is properly predicted in this case (max errors lower than 1%).

The accuracy of the permeability detection has been studied through a sensitivity analysis considering: degrees of deviations in the range of the lowest experimental errors typically achievable in permeability measurements (10-20%), arbitrariness of permeability distributions and effect of sensor positions. Figure 6, 7 and 8 summarize important outcomes of such analysis. In Figure 6, a sinusoidal permeability profile, showing a variation up to 10% of the mean value, is given. The algorithm accurately detects the permeability profile, exploiting the pressure information of the sensor (small oscillations occur close to the sensor point as discussed before). In this case, the real/estimated flow-front comparison is omitted, since the permeability deviations of such low percentages have a negligible effect on the flow-front position compared with the undisturbed condition.

In the case of Figure 7, an arbitrary permeability distribution is considered. Here, the methodology has been applied for three different sensor positions. It is noticeable that the sensor location has practically no influence to the permeability reconstruction, which in all three situations is very precise. Analogous conclusions can be drawn looking at the flow-fronts' comparison in Figure 8. Since no permeability or flow-front information can be derived before the resin reaches the sensor, it can be placed as close as possible to the inlet gate (according to the considerations in [10], the minimum distance from the gate has to be chosen in order that $|p_{in} - p_s|$ is lower than the measurement uncertainty at every time).

4 Conclusions and outlook

An approach to estimate current permeability values and detect their actual spatial variations during LCM

processes is investigated. The methodology is based on a numerical algorithm that analyzes pressure data from a single sensor embedded in the mold and identifies the permeability profile and flow-front advancement in rectilinear injections (one-dimensional flows). The approach is applied using data from virtual injection tests, where arbitrary permeability distributions are inputted. Results show that the proposed algorithm is able to reconstruct with great accuracy the various permeability profiles, identifying adequately both small (10%) and high (one order of magnitude) deviations from an undisturbed permeability. The flow-front advancements are also successfully predicted.

Future work aims at validating the presented methodology as well in real injection experiments and possibly extending it to resolve more complex flow cases. Since the knowledge of the effective permeability field gives information on the flow evolution and the fiber volume content distribution, the method can be prospectively applied for early identifications of flawed structures. Parts, which do not meet defined quality requirements (e.g. max deviations from nominal fiber volume content), could be detected already during the manufacturing process.

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Fig. 1. Pressure profile with two permeability zones.

Fig. 2. Pressure profile at time step t_i .

Fig. 3. Reconstruction of a constant permeability distribution: the highest deviation (about 20%) occurs close to the sensor point. The peak is avoided by application of a simple smoothing procedure.

Fig. 4. Permeability mapping in case of variation from nominal value of one order of magnitude.

Fig. 5. Real and estimated flow-fronts comparison in case of permeability distribution of Figure 4.

Fig. 6. Permeability mapping in case of very small (10%), sinusoidal deviations from nominal value.

Fig. 7. Mapping of an arbitrary permeability distribution: comparison of reconstructions from different sensor positions.

Fig. 8. Real and estimated flow-fronts comparison in case of permeability distribution of Figure 7.